

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING TERMINOLOGY

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Annotation

The aim of the research is to study the effectiveness of interactive methods and to consider the importance and features of the use of interactive methods in the classroom. One of the most important tasks of scientific work is to consider the specifics of the use of interactive methods in the teaching terminology of their effective results and use.

Key Terms –terminology, terms, interactive method, interactive techniques, problematic situation, selective discussion, educator, approach.

INTRODUCTION

The National Program of Personnel Training of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes measures and goals for educating the younger generation to think independently¹. The solution to this problem also depends in many ways on the use of interactive teaching methods in organized learning processes.

Nowadays, the effective organization of the lesson, in turn, shows the importance of the widespread use of interactive methods. Interactive methods, in turn, can be interpreted as a factor that positively affects the process of mastering students, as well as in the full performance of their duties in revealing the purpose

¹ "National Program of Personnel Training" of the Republic of Uzbekistan T., 1997

of the lesson. Despite of the important aspects and effects of the use of interactive methods in the teaching process have been extensively learned and discussed by many researchers and scientists, also through this research importance of interactive methods in the teaching of specific terms has been extensively studied. These questions can be discussed in the research:

- What is the interactive method itself and why should it be widely used in the classroom?
- What methods are included in the interactive methods?
- How effective is the use of interactive methods in the process of teaching specific terms?

II BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

First of all, if we clarify the concept of "interactive", the word "interactive" is derived from the English word "interact". "Inter" means mutual, "act" means to work, to work, "active" means active². Thus, the method of interactive teaching is, first of all, interactive teaching, in the course of which the interaction between the teacher and the student takes place, encouraging them to be active.

The interactive method is aimed at developing personal qualities, activating the acquisition of knowledge by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process. Using interactive methods can help increase lesson effectiveness. One of the main directions in improving teaching methods today is the introduction of interactive teaching and learning methods. All science teachers are increasingly using interactive methods in their teaching. As a result of using interactive methods, students develop the skills of independent thinking, analysis,

²Turdiev N.SH., Asadov YU.M., Akbarova S.N., Temirov D.SH. Educational technologies aimed at developing students' competencies in the general secondary education system. // Textbook. (Part I). Tashkent, 2015. - 160 b; B. 5-6 b.

drawing conclusions, expressing their opinions, defending them on the basis of them, healthy communication, discussion, debate.

III METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

Interactive activities in the classroom involve the establishment and development of dialogic communication that leads to mutual understanding, collaboration, and joint resolution of common but important issues for each participant. The interactive method removes the dominance of one speaker over another.

In the process of dialogical teaching, students learn to think critically, solve complex problems based on the analysis of conditions and relevant information, to guess alternative ideas, to connect and make informed decisions, to participate in discussions, to communicate with others. . To do this, individual, pair and group work is organized in the classroom, research projects, role-playing games are used, work with documents and various sources of information is carried out, and creative work is used.

In addition to pure learning objectives, the following aspects are important for the organizers of interactive learning³:

- Understand the values of others in the process of group interaction;
- The need to interact with others and the need for their help;
- Encourage students to act and increase the process of logical thinking;
- Encourage quick thinking by organizing unexpected situations;
- Constant and frequent use of interactive methods not only increase students' knowledge capacity, but also increase their vocabulary with an emphasis on terminology;
- Development of competitive mood in students.

³ <http://manzura90.zn.uz/interfaol-metodlar/>

Therefore, there are two key functions that interactive learning groups need to perform in order to be successful:

The condition for solving a learning problem with a pragmatic aspect of teaching;

Addressing educational issues (assisting team members in collaborative work, developing behavioral norms)⁴.

B. Instruments

These interactive methods are among the most effective methods used in the non-traditional organization of lessons. Interactive methods also include a number of techniques that in turn encourage activity and focus on an unconventional approach to the lesson and collaboration. From the point of view of scientific work, as part of the study of the effectiveness of the use of interactive methods in teaching terminology, we can introduce a set of interactive methods and techniques applied to students as tools of scientific work. The most widely used of these are: heuristic conversation; discussion method; mental attack; round table; the method of business games; problematic situation; selective discussion of practical work and user-friendly interactive teaching methods with another individual teacher.

C. Participants

In the process of learning, the interaction of students means that each of them individually contributes to a specific relationship, sharing mutual knowledge, ideas and ways of working. At the same time, all this is done in an atmosphere of mutual goodwill and support. This, in turn, not only provides an opportunity to acquire new knowledge, but also develops the cognitive activity itself, leading it to higher levels of cooperation and collaboration. The participants of the interactive method are teachers who use the interactive method in the course of the lesson, as well as test

⁴ <https://znanio.ru/media/oqitishning-interfaol-metodi-2522604>

work with the results of students' knowledge to see the effect. The participants of the interactive method are, in a word, individuals who learn in the learning process.

D. Data Collection and analysis

In general, all the interactive methods that are organized and used in the educational process can be divided into 2 types, taking into account the participation of the oral process: verbal and nonverbal methods⁵.

The verbal method is the use of verbal speech activities in which, in addition to the units of speech we use, include timbre, pause, intonation, resonance, clarity, oratory, pronunciation, word sensitivity, and more. The nonverbal method includes a set of actions, emotions, facial expressions, hand movements, gestures, body posture and movement. Verbal methods are the most commonly used method in language teaching, in that they help the learner to know and express what they have learned in speech, as well as to broaden their horizons. Not only in the teaching English terminology, but also in the process of training students in other fields, the "open-ended" questions that fall into the verbal category of interactive methods, that is, the situation that requires situational analysis, not a single "correct" answer. Asking questions aimed at being able to articulate different perspectives on is one of the most effective ways of teaching and learning. This method allows students to express their opinions openly without fear during the lesson, allowing learners to express both their right and wrong views. This will be the basis for more effective development of language skills of young generation by creating and analyzing problem situations in the process of language learning. It should be noted that the use of interactive methods in improving the quality of education, in addition to increasing the scope of knowledge than traditional methods, develops the intellectual horizons of learners, to act in solidarity and to unite in the pursuit of a common goal.

⁵ Abdukodirov A., Ishmukhamedov R., Pardaev A. Innovative technologies in education (practical recommendations for teachers of educational institutions) .- T .: Istedod, 2008.-180 pages.

For those who study in non-philological educational institutions, these qualities are the most essential. Using interactive methods, they can be prepared quickly.

Why this type of training?, What are the causes ?, What is the cause of the problem? What is the exact solution to the problem? How to determine the solution? It prepares educators to act on the basis of a series of questions and to find answers and solutions to the questions through the right consideration. When the process of memorization is taken into account in the functioning of the brain, memory is the most important factor for a person, and knowledge can be acquired through memory. The use of interactive methods not only makes the learning process more interesting, but also contributes to the formation of language skills and the memory of information and knowledge learned and discussed in the course using interactive methods. It will be the basis for lifelong or long-term retention in the database. The teacher's question, which is used in the process of interactive methods, should be used as a powerful tool to grow and develop the student's thinking. There are 2 types of questions in terms of the interactive method. The first type of question limits the student's range of thinking and directs him or her to a simple reconstruction of what he or she already knows. Such questions do not focus on the process of thinking, but on the restoration of the acquired knowledge, that is, serve as a basis for strengthening the acquired knowledge.

The second type of questions are those that encourage thinking, thinking, imagining, creating, or analyzing. Such questions not only raise the level of thinking, but also encourage students to feel that their opinions are important. The teacher is important in this process and he has to follow some rules. The study of specific terminology is important in the process of training non-philological educational institutions' students; specific terms are required to be studied not only in their native language but also in the foreign language (English) they are learning. In the process of teaching a foreign language, the questions asked by the teacher should be within the requirements:

- ✓ Questions should be clear and concise;

- ✓ Ask only one question at a time;
- ✓ The question is directly related to the topic;
- ✓ The question is within the scope of the study;
- ✓ Organization based on terminology;
- ✓ Not far from national traditions;
- ✓ Influence the thinking process;
- ✓ Targeted questioning;
- ✓ Conformity to the learner's knowledge potential;
- ✓ Age-appropriate for the learner;
- ✓ Formulation of questions that meet cultural and ethical rules;
- ✓ Focus on questions that help build communication skills;
- ✓ Influenced by factors that shape social and cultural capacity;
- ✓ Questions that have a solution and an answer;
- ✓ All the words in the question are clear to the reader;
- ✓ Try to have several alternative answers to each question.

Composing questions and passing them on to students requires great skill on the part of the teacher, with the emphasis on whether the questions are adapted to analysis and synthesis, and on the scope of thinking from specific to general or from general to specific. This makes it easier for students to think and answer the question. However, you should avoid asking questions that only answer “yes” or “no”, “right” or “wrong”. Ask students questions that they can answer based on their own experiences. Students need to use more questions to express their point of view.

IV. RESULTS

Through an interactive teaching method, students' collaborative activities become not only collaborative activities of the teaching process due to the teacher's participation in discussions, but also become a real creative productive activity of the individual's social relations. Collaborative learning is a self-acquired knowledge that directly affects their inner world and is a key educational function of the learning process. They're compared interactive methods with conventional methods as a

result of a test conducted to study the effectiveness of the use of interactive methods in the teaching of terms. And we obtained the following result (see figure 1).

Figure 1. Comparative analysis of methods

We have listed above a number of the functional processes of the interaction of interactive methods. In order to generalize them, we called the impact on knowledge by generalizing the positive qualities such as increasing the level of knowledge, memory, easy learning of terms and the ability to use them independently in activities, increasing mental ability. The second group, called Worldview, included all the effects of expanding the student's horizons through interactive methods, developing the ability to find easy or useful ways out of any problem situation, and being able to express themselves freely on any topic. . The next section introduced ethics as an area of educational influence that shapes cultural ability, encourages teamwork, teaches team members to support and assist each other at all times, and to help people in any situation in social life. Rapid action, quick thinking towards quick results, qualities that encourage you to find quick and easy ways out of difficult situations, have been included in the scope of quality influence called fast action. And as another proof that we can see all the positive aspects achieved through the use of interactive methods in all areas, it is given in the diagram above.

V. DISCUSSION

There are many types of interactive methods, which are selected and prepared according to the nature of the lesson topic and the intended purpose. It should be noted that the organizer of the course process can choose a method from the point of view of the lesson and the topic of the curriculum, as well as introduce a variety of interactive techniques through a creative approach. When we say technique, we do not mean a technical device, but a method that belongs to a small category and is used with modifications by a slightly different approach to the newly formed method. There are specific requirements for the readiness of students to participate in interactive lessons, which include the acquisition of knowledge necessary for active participation in the lesson, readiness for communication, interaction, independent thinking, self-expression, independent expression and defense skills, and so on.

Using the right methods will make the training fun and effective. Along with water, it is the basis for long-term storage in learners' memories. This is because interactive methods can attract even the most irresponsible student to the lesson, who is actively involved in the learning process, among others. It is well known that the process by which a person participates, rather than what he hears and sees, and many things in the process are stored in memory for a long time.

Interactive methods show the importance of the following concepts. These must first be learned by the student himself, otherwise no one can teach him anything. The teacher organizes the process that helps students to "create" knowledge, that is, to master it independently. Knowledge does not appear as it is, it does not stand ready in existence, and it is shaped by man.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, interactive learning allows you to solve several problems at once. All of these issues are related to the content of the lesson and serve to fully disclose the goals and objectives. The main purpose of effective activities is to develop students' communication skills, strengthen the acquired knowledge, help to

establish emotional connections between students, help students to work together, that is, to form a sense of community, ensures the fulfillment of educational tasks in the team by teaching them to work towards a common goal, to listen to the opinions of their peers. It is in the future that it will be able to make a significant contribution to the enrichment of terminology, both in terms of knowledge and in terms of morality. Also, as a positive result of many interactive lessons, the practice shows that the use of interactive methods in the classroom reduces the nervous tension of students. They allow them to focus on the main issues of the lesson topic by changing the form of their activities as a result of the use of interactive methods.

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